

1 Supplementary material

2 **Application of Physics-Informed Neural Networks to**
3 **predict concentration profiles in gradient liquid**
4 **chromatography**

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17 **Disclaimer:** the training datasets for $x = 1$ are shown below. Due to the small values of τ_p ,
18 the injection pulses have not been presented in the plots as well as the modifier curves at $x = 0$.

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20 **Fig. S1.** *Binary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
21 model training under different inlet concentration conditions. From left to right, the peaks
22 (orange curves) correspond to the conditions: $y=16$; $y=11$; $y=7.5$.

23

24 **Fig. S2.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 25 model training under varying inlet concentration conditions. From left to right, the peaks
 26 represented by blue and orange curves refer to the conditions: $y_{0,1}=3.90$; $y_{0,2}=2.50$; $y_{0,3}=1.85$.

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28 **Fig. S3.** *Binary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 29 model training under different injection time conditions. From left to right, the peaks (orange
 30 curves) correspond to the conditions: $\tau_p=0.23$; $\tau_p=0.9$; $\tau_p=0.2$.

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32 **Fig. S4.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 33 model training under varying injection time conditions. From left to right, the peaks represented
 34 by blue and orange curves refer to the conditions: $\tau_p=0.25$; $\tau_p=0.15$; $\tau_p=0.10$.

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36 **Fig. S5. Binary system:** Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network

37 model training under different τ_g . From left to right, the peaks (orange curves) correspond to

38 the conditions: $\tau_g=25$; $\tau_g=40$; $\tau_g=70$.

39

40 **Fig. S6.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 41 model training under varying τ_g . From left to right, the peaks represented by blue and orange
 42 curves refer to the conditions: $\tau_g=20$; $\tau_g=30$; $\tau_g=50$.

43

44 **Fig. S7.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 45 model training under varying τ_g . From left to right, the peaks represented by blue and orange
 46 curves refer to the conditions: $\tau_g=2$; $\tau_g=3$; $\tau_g=5$.

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48 **Fig. S8.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 49 model training under a nonlinear gradient of modifier (the α value characterizes the gradient –
 50 see Eq. (35)). From left to right, the peaks represented by blue and orange curves refer to the
 51 conditions: $\alpha=0.9$; $\alpha=0.8$; $\alpha=0.7$.

52

53 **Fig. S9.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 54 model training under varying S . From left to right, the peaks represented by blue and orange
 55 curves refer to the conditions: $S=13$; $S=9$; $S=7$.

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57 **Fig. S10.** *Binary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 58 model training under different Pe_a . From top to bottom, the peaks (orange curves) correspond
 59 to the conditions: $Pe_a=12.5$; $Pe_a=7.5$; $Pe_a=5$.

60

61 **Fig. S11.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
62 model training under varying Pe_a . From top to bottom, the peaks represented by blue and
63 orange curves refer to the conditions: $Pe_a=50$; $Pe_a=30$; $Pe_a=20$.

64

65 **Fig. S12.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 66 model training under varying Pe_{a_2} . From top to bottom, the peaks represented by blue and
 67 orange curves refer to the conditions: $Pe_{a_2}=110$; $Pe_{a_2}=70$; $Pe_{a_2}=50$.

68

69 **Fig. S13.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 70 model training under varying $\Delta\varphi$. From left to right, the peaks represented by blue and orange
 71 curves refer to the conditions: $\Delta\varphi=0.4$; $\Delta\varphi=0.3$; $\Delta\varphi=0.2$.

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73

74 **Fig. S14.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 75 model training under varying inlet concentration conditions and τ_g . The peaks represented by
 76 blue, orange and purple curves refer to the conditions: $y_{0,1}=2$ $\tau_g=25$; $y_{0,2}=2$ $\tau_g=30$; $y_{0,3}=4$
 77 $\tau_g=30$, respectively.

78

79

80 **Fig. S15.** *Ternary system:* Graphical representation of the dataset utilized for neural network
 81 model training under varying injection time conditions and S . The peaks represented by blue,
 82 orange, and purple curves refer to the conditions: $\tau_p=0.025$ $S=10$; $\tau_p=0.05$ $S=10$; $\tau_p=0.05$
 83 $S=12$, respectively.

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87 Furthermore, for the purpose of ascertaining whether Model A2 is able to handle the cases
88 realized in the preliminary phase of the research, associated with Model A1, Model A2 was
89 trained on the datasets Figs. S1-S4. The prediction results for each dataset are summarised
90 below.

92 **Fig. S16. Binary system:** Comparison of the results obtained by Model A2 with the ED model's
93 numerical solutions for a case study involving various inlet concentration conditions. The \mathcal{L}_2
94 error was 0.0138.

95

96 **Fig. S17.** *Ternary system:* Comparison of the results obtained by Model A2 with the ED model's
 97 numerical solutions for a case study involving various inlet concentration conditions. The \mathcal{L}_2
 98 error was 0.0123 and 0.0122, respectively.

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101 **Fig. S18.** *Binary system:* Comparison of the results obtained by Model A2 with the ED model's
 102 numerical solutions for a case study involving various injection time conditions. The \mathcal{L}_2 error
 103 was 0.1123.

104

105 **Fig. S19.** *Ternary system:* Comparison of the results obtained by Model A2 with the ED model's
 106 numerical solutions for a case study involving various injection time conditions. The \mathcal{L}_2 error
 107 was 0.0313 and 0.0513, respectively.

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109 **Glossary**

110 *Acronyms*

- 111 AD – automatic differentiation
- 112 ANN – artificial neural network
- 113 ED – equilibrium-dispersive
- 114 GLC – gradient liquid chromatography
- 115 L-BFGS – limited memory Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno
- 116 LC – liquid chromatography
- 117 LHS – Latin Hypercube Sampling
- 118 LSS – linear solvent strength
- 119 N – number of theoretical plates
- 120 NICP – number of internal collocation points
- 121 NN – neural network
- 122 NS – number of subdomains
- 123 OCFE – Orthogonal Collocation on Finite Element
- 124 ODE – ordinary differential equation
- 125 PCC – periodic counter-current chromatography
- 126 PDE – partial differential equation
- 127 PINN – Physics-Informed Neural Network
- 128 WENO – a weighted essentially non-oscillatory (WENO)

129 *Symbols, units and other terms*

- 130 α – adjustable parameter to modulate the modifier concentration [-]
- 131 ε_t – total column porosity [-]
- 132 ε_e – bulk porosity [-]

- 133 φ_0 – fraction of a modifier in the mobile phase [v/v]
- 134 $\Delta\varphi$ – change in modifier fraction between the beginning and the end of the gradient [v/v]
- 135 θ – the parameters of the neural network
- 136 $\lambda_{\mathcal{R}}$ – the weight term associated with the residual part of the loss function
- 137 $\lambda_{B.C.2}$ – the weight term of the second boundary loss term
- 138 \mathcal{L}_2 – relative L2 error
- 139 ξ – input parameter in Model A2 allows for handling a broader range of scenarios where input
- 140 parameters, such as the time gradient, the Peclet number, or others can be varied
- 141 τ_g – the duration of the gradient [-]
- 142 τ_p – injection time [-]
- 143 τ_b – time when the gradient reaches the column inlet
- 144 ω – input parameter, denoting inlet concentration and injection time
- 145 c – concentration in a mobile state [g/dm³]
- 146 c_r – reference variable assumed to be equal 1 [g/dm³]
- 147 D_a – apparent dispersion coefficient [-]
- 148 D_L – the dispersion coefficient [m²/s]
- 149 K_1, \dots, K_{N_c} – equilibrium constants
- 150 L – column length [m]
- 151 Model A1 – physics-informed neural network, developed in the first phase of research for
- 152 prediction of concentration profiles under linear GLC conditions
- 153 Model A2 – PINN model, which has expanded and evolved from the Model A1
- 154 N – the number of theoretical plates
- 155 $N_{B.C.}$ – boundary points at the two ends of the domain
- 156 N_c – the number of components
- 157 N_{Data} – experimentally derived data points

- 158 $N_{I.C.}$ – the number of points associated with the initial conditions
- 159 $N_{\mathcal{R}}$ – the number of collocation points inside the domain
- 160 n – the number of spatiotemporal points
- 161 $Pe_{a,i}$ – apparent Peclet number, where $i = 1$ and $i = 2$ refer to analytes, whereas $i = 3$ to modifier
- 162 Q – dimensionless concentrations in the stationary phase;
- 163 q – concentration in a stationary state [g/dm^3]
- 164 q_i – adsorption model
- 165 q_s – saturation capacity
- 166 S – parameter describing the organic modifier dependence of the adsorption process [-]
- 167 t – time [s]
- 168 t_0 – total time during in which the movement of the solute is monitored [s]
- 169 t_p – injection time [s]
- 170 x – normalized space coordinate along the column axis [-]
- 171 y – dimensionless concentration in the mobile phase
- 172 y_0 – the inlet concentration [-]
- 173 z – coordinate along the column axis [m]